

The Catalyst Project:
Open Collaborative Cloud Project for
Latin America and Africa

Community Onboarding Document

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Section 1: Introduction and overview of the Catalyst Project

The Catalyst Project is a collaborative project among [6 non-profit organisations](#) funded by the Chan Zuckerberg Initiative. The project aims to provide interactive cloud infrastructure to biomedical communities in Latin America and Africa.

Section 1.1: About this document

This document is aimed at introducing the Catalyst Project to community partners. It is a living document that will be constantly updated with feedback from stakeholders including project team and community partners.

Section 1.1.1 The structure of this evolving document

The document is arranged in sections. The first section provides an overview of the Catalyst Project. The second section then introduces the services that will be provided to community partners through the Catalyst Project. Section three lists some of the expectations from community partners participating in the Catalyst Project. In section four, we introduce some possible frequently asked questions that community partners might be interested in. Finally, we provide an appendix at the end of the document to further provide additional information about the project goals and the project team.

Section 1.1.2: Who this document is for

This document is intended for representatives of communities in Latin America and Africa including hub champions, community champions and the leadership of communities that will participate in this project to have a common background of the project goals and activities.

Section 1.2: Project glossary

We have some specific terms that we use in the Catalyst Project. Table 1 below shows the key terms. If we missed anything, please let us know so that we can keep updating and evolving it!

Table 1: Terminology Definitions

Term	Definition
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Community partner	A community that agrees to be part of the Catalyst Project
Community leaders	Community leadership members. Members of the community that approves the community engagement with the Catalyst Project
Hub champion	A technical member of the community that may or may not be part of the community leadership that will be responsible for technically supporting community members on using the cloud infrastructure.
Community champion	A member of the community that may or may not be part of the community leadership that will be responsible for supporting the community inclusion, participating in governance working sessions, and in open science training. The hub and community champion can be the same or a different person
Project Team	The 6 non-profit organisers that are funded for Chan Zuckerberg Initiative to deliver the project

Section 1.3: Project code of conduct

The Catalyst Project aims to create an inclusive and welcoming environment for every community. In order to be inclusive, we believe that we need the voice of communities to participate in creating a document that reflects the values of all communities.

Our initial thoughts on engagement guidelines largely resonate with the 2i2c and the OLS codes of conducts.

During our governance and sustainability sessions, we will work on developing a participating guideline that works for everyone.

Section 2: Services Community Partners can expect from participation in the Catalyst Project

This section outlines what hubs or community partners can expect from their engagement in the Catalyst Project.

Section 2.1 Cloud Infrastructure

The project will provide interactive cloud infrastructure to communities for the project's duration. We aim for each community to have at least one year of access to this interactive cloud infrastructure. See [the 2i2c service documentation](#) to get an idea for what this infrastructure will be like.

We can support two programming languages (Python and R), and the target workflow is interactive computing. This can be in data analysis, training or other formats that require continued interaction with the infrastructure.

Section 2.2: Training for community leaders

Figure 1. Roadmap of the project from the perspective of communities and project team. Click [here](#) for a bigger version of the Figure

One of the objectives of this project is to build capacity, and to achieve that, we have envisioned a few training programs to support communities.

1. **Train the Trainer Workshop:** We hope to build training capacity in community leaders including hub and community champions. To achieve this, community leaders will have the opportunity to participate in a "Train the Trainer" workshop based on The Carpentries Instructor Training. The workshop aims to develop training capacity in community leaders to enable community leaders to conduct training workshops for community members.
2. **End-User Workshop:** We will develop training materials for communities with the help of community leaders. We will also translate some of the training materials into Spanish to support Spanish-speaking communities in Latin America. Once these training materials are developed and community leaders take the "Train the Trainer" workshop, community leaders will take the end-user training to understand how community members may perceive the training materials. Feedback from community leaders will be used to improve the training materials.
3. **OLS open science training and mentoring:** An important part of the project is to enable open science. Community leaders and some community members will have the opportunity to participate in 16-week cohort training to improve their

understanding of open science and to develop skills needed for communities to participate in open science.

Table 2: Catalyst Project Capacity Building Trainings for Communities

Training	Who should Take the training	Who organises the training	How long it takes
Train the Trainer	Hub champion (highly recommended), community champion (recommended), community leaders (optional)	The Carpentries	1-2 days with 6 hours per day.
End-User Workshop	Hub champion (highly recommended), community champion (recommended), community leaders (optional)	2i2c	1 weeks- 2 hours per day for 5 days
Open Science training and mentorship	Community champion (highly recommended), community members (highly recommended), hub champion (recommended), community leaders (recommended)	OLS	16 weeks - 5 hours per week (cohort and mentorship call are 1.5 and 0.5 hours respectively. Mentees are also required to do so homework and work on their project which takes about 3 hours per week)

Section 2.3: Honoraria

The project will be offering honoraria for certain categories of community member participation. An honorarium is a one-time, token payment granted to recognise an individual's contribution to the Catalyst project.

Please note that the recipient of the honorarium is not permitted to set the honorarium amount. The Catalyst Project Manager will share further details with contributors on how to receive their respective due amount. Communities might choose to decide if they want to

share part of the honoraria with any team members performing support activities, such as administration tasks. Communities might also opt to decline receiving honoraria.

Section 2.4: Who to contact

Currently, the contact person on the project team is Tajuddeen Gwadabe (tajuddeen@we-are-ols.org). Tajuddeen Gwadabe is the programme manager on the project and will be happy to assist with questions regarding the cloud infrastructure and the project.

As the project continues to evolve, we expect to provide contacts for different elements of the project such as partnerships, training, and technology.

Section 3: Catalyst Project expectations from Communities

During the process of establishing a partnership with you, you'll be sent a term of service document. This section of the onboarding document gives some more details about our expectations from your participation in the project.

Section 3.1: Communities we work with

The project supports communities in Latin America and Africa that conduct training and/or research in the biomedical sciences. These communities are often parts of non-profit organisations, research centres, and public universities with an interest in open science principles.

Section 3.2: Community point of contact

The project requires communities to identify two main points of contact. However, for smaller communities, one contact person may be able to handle both roles.

1. **Hub Champion:** A hub champion has the *technical knowledge* of user workflows and ideally experience with cloud infrastructure and support the community in a technical capacity
2. **Community Champion:** A community champion may or may not have technical expertise. The major responsibilities of a community champion include:
 - a. Liaising with the project team and other community champions to build collaborations
 - b. Organising community members to participate in the OLS open science training and mentoring programme

The responsibilities of both the hub champion and community champion may include other related activities not mentioned above. Once the hub and community champions have been identified by the communities, please notify the project manager of the Catalyst Project (Tajuddeen - tajuddeen@we-are-ols.org)

Section 3.3: Training for community members

After the community leaders go through the “Train the Trainer” and end-user workshops, community leaders are encouraged to deliver the end-user training to their community members. The project team is interested in understanding the successes and challenges of such training.

Section 3.4: Interviews and Feedback

The Catalyst project team will interact with community leaders throughout the project to understand what works for communities and areas where we can improve the services. We also intend to get feedback from the communities on the overall process and concerns on the sustainability of the project.

Section 4: Frequently Asked Questions

This section introduces some possible frequently asked questions that community leaders might be interested in.

Section 4.1: Cloud Service

How long will you have access to the cloud infrastructure?

Our aim is for each community to have access to the cloud infrastructure for at least one (1) year. Communities that join the project earlier may have access beyond one year.

Will there be a limit to the infrastructure?

We do not envision limiting access for communities based on our estimated usage from other communities. However, if the usage exceeds our expected estimates, we will discuss with communities on ways forward.

What type of support do we expect for the cloud infrastructure?

2i2c will manage the backend infrastructure and support communities in solving backend issues such as outages. However, the project team does not have the capacity to support communities on the day-to-day usage of the infrastructure. For that reason, we expect communities to have a hub-champion responsible for supporting community members with executing their workflows on the infrastructure.

What if we want to use the infrastructure after the project ends?

If you want to continue using the infrastructure after the project ends, please contact 2i2c (partnerships@2i2c.org) to find out more about their pricing. We aim to estimate the consumption of each community throughout the project to support communities in making informed decisions.

Section 4.2: Training programs

How long is the “Train the Trainer” workshop?

The “Train the Trainer” workshop takes about 1-2 days. But we aim for a 1-day workshop.

How long is the end-user workshop?

We do not have a clear sense of the time requirement for the end-user workshop. However, we expect the workshop to take 2 hours a day for 5 days.

What is the format of the OLS open science training and mentoring programme?

The current format of the cohort is for individual(s) (mentees) to propose an open science project they are interested in working on through the cohort. OLS will then match the projects to mentors who assist mentees in working on the project while taking workshops throughout the 16 weeks. For more information on the types of projects, training content please visit the [OLS website](#)

What is the time requirement for the OLS open science training and mentorship cohort per week?

Mentees dedicate about 5 hours per week to attend cohort/mentor calls and do other self-guided activities.

Section 4.3: Interviews and feedback

How often will communities be interviewed?

The project team plans to have a couple of interviews with the communities as the project progresses. However, these interviews will be scheduled at the convenience of community leaders.

How do we give feedback to the project team?

Our current setup for all feedback is to be sent to Tajuddeen Gwadabe (tajuddeen@openlifesci.org). We may, however in the future, provide alternative means of sharing feedback. Feedback requests may also come in a Google Form or questionnaire. The aim is for the project team to improve our processes and also to find sustainable solutions to concerns from communities.

What did we miss?

If you have questions that are not listed below, please contact our programme manager Tajuddeen at tajuddeen@openlifesci.org. We welcome your feedback and input to continuously improve this section and document.

Appendix

The goals of the Catalyst Project

Cloud infrastructure can make science more open and inclusive. But there are many challenges to making the cloud accessible to global communities. Communities need:

- Access to infrastructure that aligns with the values of open communities
- Training relevant to a local context.
- Capacity to organise training around this infrastructure.

Our overarching goal is to provide these as a service to communities in Latin America and Africa, both to impact these communities and to learn and explore the right models to do so.

Figure 2: Team composition on project goals.

Legend

The organisational logos mentioned in Figure 2 above refers to the following organisations working on the project.

2i2c 2i2c

 The Carpentries

 MetaDocencia

Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement

OLS

Invest in Open Infrastructure

Goal 1: Infrastructure. Deploy and manage open cloud infrastructure for under-resourced communities in Latin America and Africa.

- Subgoal 1a: Deploy dedicated infrastructure. Deploy interactive computing hubs for target communities adapted to biomedical use cases.
- Subgoal 1b: Ongoing support and development. Improvements to infrastructure as needed for biomedical environments.

Goal 2: Use-case training. Create training and pedagogical content to assist others in using this infrastructure for cloud-based science workflows.

- Subgoal 2a: Content creation. Create learning material for open workflows in the cloud.
- Subgoal 2b: Adapt materials to local communities. Contextualise for biomedical communities in Latin America and Africa.

Goal 3: Capacity building. Build capacity for technical, pedagogical, and leadership skills within these communities.

- Subgoal 3a: Train the trainers' workshops. Teach community leaders about the cloud workflows our infrastructure enables and how to share knowledge with others.
- Subgoal 3b: Open leadership practices. Run cohorts of open leaders training for leaders in partner communities.
- Subgoal 3c: Infrastructure secondment. Partnership with the National University of Cordoba to train in cloud infrastructure.

Goal 4: Sustainable models. Identify a participatory service model to sustain, scale, and generalise impact for global communities.

- Subgoal 4a: Explore collaboration structures. What collaborative model can best meet the deliverables above? How can we sustain or scale this model?
- Subgoal 4b: Participatory governance models. How to build mechanisms for oversight, accountability, and participation with partner communities?
- Subgoal 4c: Sustainability. Synthesise our learning and describe how similar services could follow this model.

The Catalyst Project team

The Catalyst Project team consists of six open science organisations working collaboratively to achieve the goals of the project. Each of them is focused on specific aspects of the project and on a set of goals that will be built towards the overall project goals.

2i2c

[2i2c](#)'s mission is to make research and education more impactful, accessible, and delightful by developing, operating, and supporting infrastructure for interactive computing.

Project role: 2i2c designs, deploys, and maintains JupyterHubs on multiple cloud platforms and is responsible for providing the infrastructure for the communities on the project. 2i2c also develops technical and user documentation that will be used for community training.

The Carpentries

[The Carpentries](#) build global capacity in essential data and computational skills for conducting efficient, open, and reproducible research through training, community building, and curriculum development.

Project role: The Carpentries will connect communities with the project, focusing on the African continent. The organisation will also support the development and delivery of training at several stages of the project.

MetaDocencia

[MetaDocencia](#)

MetaDocencia's mission is to advance innovation with a local perspective that responsibly builds scientific and technical capacities through the co-creation of networks, learning spaces, and accessible resources for Spanish-speaking communities.

Project role: MetaDocencia will identify communities in Latin America to participate in Catalyst, onboarding and connecting them to other project partners. MetaDocencia will also assist with contextualising lesson materials to Latin American audiences, designing the Catalyst project's governance, developing and improving documentation.

CSCCE

[The Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement \(CSCCE\)](#)

CSCCE is a training and research centre to support and study the emerging field of scientific community engagement.

Project role: CSCCE is working as part of the strategy team to support the initial setup of the core project team. CSCCE is also supporting discussions about the community engagement activities of the grant and resharing learnings about team-building and community building more broadly.

IOI

[Invest in Open Infrastructure](#) (IOI)

IOI works to increase the investment in and adoption of open infrastructure to further equitable access to and participation in research and to provide targeted, evidence-based guidance and support to institutions and funders of open infrastructure.

Project role: IOI will conduct initial research in governance activities and design an early-stage governance and sustainability plan, which will be piloted by project teams and participating community members.

OLS

[Open Life Science](#) (OLS)

OLS is an open science capacity building organisation with a mission to upskill, connect and support a distributed network of ambassadors enabling the adoption of open science principles in their local communities.

Project role: OLS hosts the programme manager for Catalyst and provides open science training and mentoring for participating community members.